

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

**“Let’s Build our SFSC”
Event Validation Report
Responsible Partner: UNIMOS**

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“Let’s Build our SFSC!” Event Validation Report - Lithuania

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of UNIMOS Foundation for the organisation and validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in Lithuania organised on 27th March 2023. This event is an online brokerage and networking event, to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agroBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agrifood sector at local level. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Let’s build our SFSC event in Lithuania.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

The “Let’s build our SFSC” in Lithuania took place on 27th March 2023. The concept selected for the organization of the event was agreed with stakeholders from Lithuania. It was designed and implemented to address Lithuanian needs identified in agroBRIDGES information and collection process, co-creation activities and consultations with Lithuanian experts.

Considering UNIMOS’ previous experiences on working with Lithuanian agri-food stakeholders, recommendations of local experts on the best possible format and SMEs needs, it was decided to organize a meeting at more strategic level and for people who is used to work with networking and brokerage digital platform on daily basis. Having in mind that in Lithuania there is a need for stable funding, more collaboration and systemic support for the development of SFSC, the chosen format was focused on building, financing, and boosting strategic collaboration based on boosting orchestration of support services and inter-project synergies generation to promote, finance and build SFSC in Lithuania. This approach was selected with the aim to offer SMEs, farmers and other agri-food supply chain actors concrete and tangible opportunities for the development of new SFSC and marketing models.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers	Location
Session #1	Opening session: Introduction and presentation of agroBRIDGES project	13:00 – 13:10	Beacon Leader Expert (UNIMOS Foundation)	Central stage
Session #2	Pool of opportunities to build and finance SFSC in Lithuania	13:10 – 13:20	Beacon Leader Expert (UNIMOS Foundation)	Central stage
Session #3	Presentation of Lithuanian Innovation Center, its offer and current innovation projects	13:20 – 13:30	Lithuanian Innovation Center expert	Central stage
Session # 4	Open discussion to design EU projects, business and innovation support services synergies implemented in Lithuania and Europe	13:30 – 13:50	All participants	Central stage
Session # 5	Closing and feedback gathering	13:50 – 14:00	Beacon Leader Expert (UNIMOS Foundation)	Central stage

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

In order to implement the event, both in-house and external personnel were involved to ensure technical and logistical smooth organization of the event.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material	In-house	1 person days
Session moderator	1	Coordination of the online session	In-house	1.5 person days
Local speaker	1	Speaker at thematic session	External	N/A
Technical facilitator	3	Coordination of technical preparation of the platform	In-house	4 person days
Local facilitator	1	Engagement and recruitment of participants	External	N/A

2.3 Event material

In order to promote and implement the event, dedicated posts for social media was prepared and posted on LinkedIn platform with the invitation to participate in the online event.

Registration form in Lithuanian was used to gather participants consent and invite them to register on the Brella platform.

Figure 1: Promotional material – Social media event announcement

Let's build our SFSC event
Networking and brokerage event for agri-food businesses, producers and HORECA

agr BRIDGES UNIMOS alliance

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101000788.

Event ended

Let's build our SFSC in Lithuania

Event by UNIMOS Alliance

Mon, Mar 27, 2023, 1:00 PM - 2:00 PM (your local time)

Online

Event link https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScLrMLO9z5IgbSaZYya1nGx9QVDX2ZdDL_dFqa94Jn4t-PK8A/viewform

Anna Bialik and 5 other attendees

Share Manage ...

Figure 2: Promotional material – Social media invitation

U. Unimos
23 marca o 08:58 · 🌐

Are you interested in Short Food Supply Chains #sfsc in #Lithuania?
Join our matchmaking event!
Unimos, as part actions in #agroBridges Project, is organising a series of matchmaking events in Beacon Regions we are responsible for: Poland, Lithuania and Latvia.... [Zobacz więcej](#)

Let's build our SFSC event
Networking and brokerage event for agri-food businesses, producers and HORECA

agr BRIDGES UNIMOS alliance THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101019786.

LINKEDIN.COM
Let's build our SFSC in Lithuania | LinkedIn
Džiaugiamės galėdami pakviesti Jus į projekto agroBRIDGES internetinį tinklavėikos ir tarpinink...

U. UNIMOS Alliance
319 followers
2w · Edited · 🌐

We cordially invite you to online event organised in the frames of [AgroBridges Project 2021-2023](#)

>>>Let's build our SFSC in Lithuania

After registration you will receive link to matchmaking platform.

#online
#event
#matchmaking
#sfsc

8

1 repost

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The engagement and promotional strategy to reach out businesses, farmers and other agri-food stakeholders included social media posts, emails and direct contacts. Special attention was put on organizations and Lithuanian stakeholders that are working in topics closely related to SFSC, like bioeconomy, agri-food innovations, digital transformation and innovation support. In many cases, the invited organizations have a wide network of partners, are members of clusters and collaborate with other business initiatives that gathers all actors from agri-food value chain relevant for the development of SFSC in Lithuania. Direct contacts and promotional activities started after the physical “Let’s meet!” events were organized (2 weeks before the event).

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Let’s build our SFSC” event in Lithuania was divided into five sessions. The first session included official opening, welcome and presentation of general information about the agroBRIDGES project, its objectives and activities. Additionally, agroBRIDGES tools were demonstrated distinguishing:

- 1) “Ready to use” tools, such as:
 - Lithuanian SFSC good practices with European examples from agroBRIDGES interactive catalogue
 - Resource catalogue
 - Multi-actor platforms (MAPs)
- 2) Tools in validation – agroBRIDGES Toolbox with examples of SFSC tools translated into Lithuanian language.

The second session was focused on presenting the pool of opportunities to build and finance SFSC in Lithuania. It included short presentation of several EU-funded projects from different financing programmes, such as COSME, Single Market Programme (SMP), Horizon 2020, among others. The following projects were presented:

- AURORA – related to food safety, quality and authenticity (Cluster Partnership 2020 with ClusterXchange mobility scheme) that offers co-financing for international short-terms exchanges;
- SUAVE – linked to boosting urban farming (Euroclusters - SMP) with lump-sums for prototyping innovations, business diagnosis, international matchmakings and prizes;
- BIO-BOOST – focused on boosting bioeconomy innovation agencies and interconnecting European innovation ecosystems (Horizon Europe) with interactive activities to be organized in Lithuania (like hackathons) or new cross-border key account management (KAM) service for SMEs based on time banking approach.

Sharing information about the Lithuanian Innovation Center, its activities, project portfolio and support services was the central topic of the third session. The following projects, services and initiatives were presented:

- AgriFoodX5.0 - about agri-food development towards Industry 5.0 (Cluster Partnership 2020 with ClusterXchange mobility scheme). The project is synergic to the AURORA project;
- EDIHLT – European Digital Innovation Hub - linked to supporting digital transformation;
- Enterprise Europe Network services - related to boosting international expansion and business matchmaking;
- TranS4MErs - project to support manufacturing SMEs by providing fast and flexible pan-European access to advanced manufacturing advice and expertise;
- EENEIC – project focused on empowering EEN network offices support potential EIC applicants, specifically women entrepreneurs and widening countries, and Seal of Excellence (SoE) holders;
- STAGE – project aimed at creating an ecosystem for the sustainability transition of European industrial SMEs.

Additionally, the general overview of the Lithuanian innovation ecosystem was showcased.

Following, an open discussion about wise synergy building among projects took place. Participants discussed on how to interconnect EU projects with business and innovation support services (DIH, EEN) to support SFSC development in Lithuania and to boost green and digital transformation of SMEs.

Figure 3: Screenshots from presentations – agroBRIDGES tools

Figure 5: Presentation – Wise synergy building

Assisting companies to grow their competitive advantage

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Strategy, development and innovation support	7
UNIMOS	3
Total	10

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Question #1: Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event	5		2		0	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Question #2: Did you find this event helpful to meet professionals and businesses you can collaborate with?	3	4	0	0	0	0
Question #3: Do you think that this event helped you see Short Food Supply Chains as a promising business alternative?	3	3	1	0	0	0
Question #4: Did you find the matching and booking of one-to-one meetings with other people useful to identify and negotiate collaborations?	2	5	0	0	0	0
Question #5: Was the event useful in supporting you to find interesting opportunities to collaborate with other businesses for the development of Short Food Supply Chains?	4	3	0	0	0	0
Question	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Question #6: Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	1	3	2	1	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The event was relevant to local agri-food ecosystem and organization, as it supported the process of orchestration of available Lithuanian and European supporting mechanisms that could finance the development of SFSC in Lithuania. It was a valuable networking and strategic discussion space that gathered diverse actors working with different EU projects and support schemes, such as business and internationalization (European Enterprise Network) support services, support for digitalization (Digital Innovation Hub) and agri-food innovation (projects financed from COSME, Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020 programmes).

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

Yes, definitely. There is a need for organizing this type of events in Lithuania. In order to engage of agri-food stakeholders that are not used to participate in online brokerage events, it would be worth considering organization of hybrid / physical meetings and/or wider variety or simpler of digital tools, including social media.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

The organization of online event took place on the Brella platform that allows virtual, physical, and hybrid events that might boost generation of new business and collaboration opportunities, as well as enable quality networking and new interconnections. The Brella platform is a very intuitive and visual friendly platform, but also requires - both from organizers, as from attendees – some digital skills, openness to learn and use new digital tools. It is an excellent tool for organizations that are already familiar with this kind of collaborative software and online matchmaking meetings (like business support organizations) but might require specialized technical competencies and good access to internet of agri-food stakeholders that are unfamiliar with this kind of tools and difficult to keep up with the accelerated digitalization. In order to engage of agri-food stakeholders that are not used to participate in online brokerage events, it would be worth considering organization of hybrid / physical meetings and/or wider variety or simpler of digital tools, including social media.

5. Conclusions

The “Let’s build our SFSC” event in Lithuania was a very good opportunity to stimulate the development of SFSC. in Lithuania by fostering and orchestrating cross-fertilisation between EU projects, as well as interconnecting strategic Lithuanian stakeholders involved in the development of agri-food sector. The design of the event with the engagement of different actors allowed the exploration and discovery of new and tangible possibilities for SFSC actors, as well as interchange of ideas and establishment of new inter-project linkages.